

TREATING AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDERS CHILDREN WITH TURKISH MUSIC AND ITS MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS

İsmail Hakkı Akyologlu¹

Abant İzzet Baysal University,
Faculty of Education,
Fine Arts Education Department,
Music Education Division, Turkey

Abstract:

Our musical instruments should be reconsidered in various sizes, for various purposes and being reexamined their effect and capabilities. The original instruments are already exceptional, colourful and they are suitable to be used for duo, trio, quatered chamber music teams (İlerici, 1964). It is seen that Autism spectrum disorders children are innate gifted in music. As they cannot communicate with the outside world and the social environment, they live in a withdrawn world. They should be ensured to interact with music starting from of pre-school ages. Considering the place, these children live and their socio-cultural environment, a different kind of style of musical therapy should be chosen for every children. The therapist is the half of the treating with music, and the other half is the child who is going to be treated. Children teach the therapist the style of the treatment. In other words, they are the teacher of the therapist, because these children lead the way through their interactive behavior, body language and sensory organs.

Keywords: music, autism spectrum disorders, Turkish

Introduction

Turks has been one of the nations who used music therapy for the patients with mental illness. Music is a stimulant which attracts attention. It organizes people`s temperament and feelings. It makes the people who are excited to calm down and makes the people

¹ Correspondence: email akyologlu_i@ibu.edu.tr

come alive who turn in on themselves. Music activities move away the patient attention from disturbing ideas and it directs attention to the patient environment. (Ruh Sağlığı S. 193 Burhanettin Canatan, 1965)

Our mind not only affects our sense and blood pressure, it also affects our genes and molecules at the same time. Hormones penetrate the various cell nuclei of the endocrine system. (Özelsel, 2002)

Our musical instruments should be reconsidered in various sizes, for various purposes and being reexamined their effect and capabilities. The original instruments are already exceptional, colorful and they are suitable to be used for duo, trio, quarted chamber music teams. (Opus 20 Türk Müziğinin Taşıdığı Değerler, Kemal İLERİCİ 1964 Ankara)

It is seen that autism spectrum disorders children are innate gifted in music. As they cannot communicate with the outside world and the social environment, they live in a withdrawn world. They should be ensured to interact with music starting from of pre-school ages. Considering the place, these children live and their socio-cultural environment, a different kind of style of musical therapy should be chosen for every children. The therapist is the half of the treating with music, and the other half is the child who is going to be treated. Children teach the therapist the style of the treatment. In other words, they are the teacher of the therapist, because these children lead the way through their interactive behavior, body language and sensory organs.

Music is a powerful stimulant, and a good educational means that helps to focus attention. Children live in their family and the society together with their own culture and social customs. When the integrity and the continuity of the triangle of Child-Family-Therapist is provided, the period of treatment will be shorter and there will be fewer sessions. The music-therapy is usually maintained with the musical instruments that plays the rhythm and the sounds at the same time. Considering Autism spectrum disorders children's culture and the customs, the teacher should use the rhythms and the musical instruments that Autism spectrum disorders children are familiar with. Later more contemporary musical instruments can be used. Today, especially len xlafon and vibrafon (ORFF instruments) that are made from tanpereman sound system are used. The trees that these instruments are made of and the musical tones of the production technique differ. Apart from these instruments, other instruments of the Turkish music should be used, and as an alternative to orff instruments, wooden and metal percussion instruments in accordance with dieses (diyez) and flats (bemol) used in Turkish folk music and classical Turkish music should be made. These instruments will be introduced made by ourselves at the end of the oral presentation session by practicing.

Autism spectrum disorders children show a big interest against the music sounds and rhythms in the surrounding environment since they are very sensitive as natural. The diversity and richness of the Turkish music and instruments are in the lead of world's music. In this wealth of melodies, the first thing should be choosing the rhythms, instruments and patterns which are interesting for the child. The correct and useful one should be revealed during one to one interaction.

The folk songs, belly dance musics and instruments should be used first during the interaction. It would be easy to apply the rhythms in 2/4, 3/4, 4/4, 5/8, 6/8, 7/8 and 9/8 (9/16). By using these melodies with the short syllables alliterative and incbag lama ives, a great enthusiasm, interest and excitement can be achieved for children. The colors (red, black, blue, green, purple ext.) and the objects (handkerchief ext.) Which are used in the verbal Turkish music would make the treatment easier together with the melody. Examples; Seftali agacları,..... The selection can be made from these folk songs for the sessions. There are also many folk songs which can be dramatized. The baglama family, davul, def, darbuka, zıl, ext. from Turkish rhythm instruments, kudum, ud, kanun, tanbur, klasik kemence, ney from classic Turkish music instruments, violin family, mandolin, piyano, org, ağız mızıkası, akordeon, flut from the modern music instruments can be used.

Conclusion

The conclusion is to have a treatment process which is appropriate when it comes to voice, tone, language, accent and speech forms of the society where the child lives with.

References

1. Canatan, B. (1965). *Ruh Sağlığı*. Konya.
2. İlerici, K. (1964). *Türk Müziğinin Taşıdığı Değerler*, *Opus*, 20.
3. Nordoff, P., Robbins, C. (1971 – 2006) *Music Therapy in Special Education*. New York.
4. Özelsel, M. (2002). *Halvette Kırk Gün*. İstanbul: Kaknüs Yayınları.
5. Reinhard, K. (1984). *Türk Halk Müziğinin Bütünlüğü Üzerine*. Ankara: Kültür ve Turizm Bakanlığı Yayınları.

İsmail Hakkı Akyođlu
TREATING AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDERS CHILDREN WITH
TURKISH MUSIC AND ITS MUSICAL INSTRUMENTS

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Special Education Research shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).